

Exploring Microstructural Evolution Induced by Dynamic Beam Shaping in Autogenous Laser Beam Welding of AA6082

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Recent advancements in dynamic beam shaping have shown the potential to revolutionise the welding process. Although this is a very attractive proposition, knowledge about the temporal and spatial response of the process to dynamic beam shaping is yet required. This study implements a multi-kW CW laser with a coherent beam combiner (CBC) and optical phased array (OPA) to modulate the fluence distribution at the microsecond scale. It investigates microstructural evolution induced by individual free-form dynamic beam profiles generated in the kHz regime and sequences of dynamic beam profiles switched at the microsecond time scale. A self-restraint cantilever setup was conducted on AA6082 1.5 mm sheets with full-penetration single bead-on-plate welds. Metallography analysis with electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) was employed to correlate material microstructure with the tested beam shapes. The results are presented to highlight the unique features of modulated fluence distribution as well as current challenges and new research avenues.

Figure 1: Impact of core-ring and tailing beam shapes to refine the microstructure and improve the joint strength during laser beam welding of AA6082 alloy [1]. Welds conducted in butt joint at 25 mm/s.

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[1] V.V. Pamarthi, T. Sun, A. Das, Q. Hayat, A. Griffiths, L. Johnson, P. Franciosa, Axisymmetric and tailing laser beam shape to steer microstructure and cracks for welding AA6082 alloy using experimental and Multiphysics model, *Mater Des* (2024).